

From Decades to Decisions: Early Indicators for Biodiversity Outcomes

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Introduction

This rapid review brings together evidence on short-term (≤ 5 years) biodiversity indicators to fill the Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting (MER) gap in the *Protecting Victoria's Environment - Biodiversity 2037* (2017) plan. It responds to the key weaknesses identified in Part A: a misalignment between 50-year habitat-suitability metrics and 5-year monitoring cycles and a lack of operational metrics that are sensitive and appropriate for Victoria's ecosystems. I focus on indicators that can be deployed or recalculated and produce clear signals for adaptive management across rivers, wetlands, lakes and riparian zones. This aligns well with Victoria's landscapes and can improve the plan's effectiveness and transparency.

This rapid review uses the PICO framework to frame the research question. The Population/Problem is defined as conservation programs in temperate ecosystems that require policy-relevant MER. The Intervention/Indicator is short-term biodiversity indicators or proxy metrics. These include: abundance or richness indices; occupancy; recruitment or juvenile ratios; eDNA detection; vegetation structural surrogates from field; and habitat-condition scores. The Comparator is defined as no indicator, status-quo monitoring, or reliance on long-horizon (e.g., 50-year) persistence/habitat-suitability models. The Outcomes (sensitivity/responsiveness) focus mainly on two aspects: first, within a ≤ 5 -year timeframe, the ability to detect the direction and magnitude of change above noise and natural variability; second, decision usefulness for adaptive management, including cost, feasibility, repeatability, timeliness and interpretability. To maximise the usefulness of the results, I narrowed the research question to explicitly target Victoria's wetlands and rivers. Therefore, my research question is: In Victoria's wetlands and rivers, do short-term (≤ 5 -year) indicators, such as occupancy, eDNA and habitat condition, provide sensitive, decision-useful signals for MER?

Although the original plan set out an MER framework to assess performance, if the monitoring indicators do not match the policy implementation timeframe, that mismatch can drive outcomes away from the plan's intent. Large audit frameworks often need ultra-long time spans to reveal trends (50 years in the plan) which cannot meet the roughly five-year management cycle (Davies et al., 2010). This can hinder mid-cycle assessments and course

corrections. By contrast, short-term indicators can provide timely feedback to support evidence-based improvements and to flag under-performance so projects can be adjusted and kept on track (Buss et al., 2015). This helps safeguard public investment and ensures the program moves in the right direction. All of this highlights the importance of using more sensitive short-term biological indicators and event-triggered mechanisms. These indicators can register directional change well within five years, even when ultimate species-persistence goals remain long-term.

Research Protocol

I conducted a rapid review guided by the PRISMA 2020 reporting checklist (Page et al., 2021), adapting the protocol to prioritise indicators that are detectable within ≤ 5 years and sensitive to biodiversity-conservation effectiveness. A rapid approach was chosen because the decision context (MER) requires near-term, timely, and actionable evidence rather than an exhaustive systematic review (Department of Environment, Land, Water and Planning, 2017). Given that the review was undertaken by a single researcher, resource constraints also favoured a rapid approach.

Search Strategy

Scopus was used to cover authoritative environmental science and ecology journals, providing reliable evidence on the sensitive biodiversity indicators central to the question. Google Scholar was added to capture policy-relevant grey literature, especially materials from programs implemented in other regions, that could offer practical insights and directions. This two-database mix balances coverage (sensitivity) with precision and stronger metadata. The publication window was set to 2010 to 2025 to emphasise recent findings. Conservation ideas and methods evolve quickly, and very early studies may be less helpful for today's decisions. Given the context and time/resource constraints, I limited sources to English and to temperate ecosystems, with priority to Australia/Victoria. Initial searches returned 138 records from Scopus and 67 top-relevance results from Google Scholar, for a total of 205 records. In the first screening round, 4 duplicates were removed, leaving 201 unique items.

Table 1. Databases and Boolean search terms.

Database	Boolean Search Terms
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Scopus	(LANGUAGE (english) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ((wetland* OR river* ORfreshwater) AND (victoria OR australia OR temperate)) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (edna OR "environmental dna" OR "habitat condition" ORmacrophyte* OR macroinvertebrate* OR ausrivias OR signal OR bioacoustic) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (indicator* OR bioassessment ORmetric* OR "index") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (monitoring OR evaluationOR "adaptive management" OR trend*)) AND PUBYEAR > 2010 ANDPUBYEAR < 2025
Google Scholar	("time to detect" OR "power to detect" OR "minimum detectable change") biodiversity (wetland OR river OR freshwater)

Screening Process

Screening was conducted by a single reviewer (the author). Inclusion and exclusion criteria were set to align the PICO framework. To limit bias under single-reviewer constraints, I logged reasons for exclusion and moved any uncertain items to a “maybe” group for further full-text assessment. The first stage involved titles and abstracts screening. I screened all 201 records, ultimately excluded 169 papers, placed 15 into the “maybe” folder. Most “maybe” papers were set aside because their abstracts indicated study locations appeared to be outside Victoria’s wetlands or rivers and offered no statement on transferability to the Victorian context. 17 items were directly moved to the “include” group. The second stage was full-text assessment. Beginning with the 17 “include” records, I assessed them in full, resulting in 1 exclusion at full text and 16 final included studies for data extraction. The full-text stage had yielded 16 included studies which meets the target for data extraction. Given sufficient included studies and resource constraints, “maybe” items were excluded from the current pool but retained as a background resource for future work.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria based on the PICO framework.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperate rivers/wetlands/lakes/riparian; Australia/Victoria prioritised; transferable temperate studies from comparable regions acceptable with rationale. • Indicators or proxy metrics deployable/re-calculable within ≤ 5 years: macroinvertebrate indices (e.g., SIGNAL2, LIFE), occupancy, recruitment/juvenile ratios, eDNA/metabarcoding, acoustic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purely marine/open-ocean; groundwater-only; estuarine studies without clear freshwater relevance. • Purely theoretical/conceptual without empirical performance; narrative pieces without methods/results. • Studies requiring >5-year horizons for first signal. • Non-credible grey literature.

<p>indices, vegetation structure/condition (UAV/satellite), habitat-condition scores.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-reviewed empirical studies, validation/method papers with applied case studies, systematic reviews/meta-analyses, and government/agency reports with primary data and transparent methods. • Outcomes report responsiveness/sensitivity (time to detect, effect size, statistical trend) and/or decision usefulness (cost/effort, repeatability, feasibility). • Date ranges from 2010 to 2025; English; full text available. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-English; Unavailable full text. • Non-temperate contexts unless methods clearly transferable.
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Data Extraction

I extracted four core data fields (See Appendix). The indicator field anchors construct validity. This matters for assessing the usefulness of the findings to my question. Time-to-signal (whether a directional change is detectable within five years) is treated as the primary policy filter. Because indicators that only move over longer horizons are not useful for a 5-year evaluation cycle. I also captured the direction and size of change as an important sensitivity metrics. They help interpret uncertainty and anticipate how results may translate to Victoria's context, supporting more accurate evaluation. Finally, I recorded the comparator/baseline (e.g., before–after with controls). Without a comparator it is hard to tell whether a change was caused by management or by natural variability. This makes the indicator genuinely decision-useful. For each paper I also added a brief comment on MER implications (cost/effort). Study quality was judged on three dimensions. First, the study's internal validity, including the rigour of the design, bias control, sampling, and stated uncertainties/limitations. Second, how quickly the signal responds and whether it carries to Victoria's wetlands and rivers. Third, the applicability, including implementation cost and the study's practical guidance for the MER framework.

Results

Across the included set, most studies were quantitative, with two syntheses/guidance documents. Empirical papers were generally high quality (multi-site

designs, clear statistics, or experimental control), while syntheses were rated uncertain because they provide frameworks rather than primary data (see Appendix). Cross-sectional gradient studies dominate for stressor–response thresholds. A smaller subset uses before–after designs that better resolve timing.

Most of the studies I reviewed show detectable improvements within a five-year (or shorter) window. A notable exception is the assessment based on crayfish biomass in south-east Australian upland streams, where the response time exceeded five years (Noble & Fulton, 2017). Such lags can undermine monitoring within a fixed evaluation cycle. By contrast, macroinvertebrate measures typically respond within weeks to months after disturbances, providing timely feedback for monitoring (Chattopadhyay et al., 2021; Morris et al., 2017). eDNA performed well for detecting presence and relative biomass, and for multi-taxa screening (Rourke et al., 2024). However, abundance estimates were less reliable than biomass proxies, and all eDNA applications required local calibration (Rourke et al., 2024). More broadly, many eDNA and trait/threshold studies were cross-sectional (Kefford et al., 2012; Schäfer et al., 2011). This means they are useful for rapid detection and screening at a single point in time, but they are not well suited to inferring recovery trends. Landscape context also mattered: near-stream forest cover consistently improved integrated ecosystem-health scores, whereas urban cover depressed them (Sheldon et al., 2012).

Taken together, the most decision-ready indicators for short MER cycles are: macroinvertebrate richness; selective stressor indices (e.g., for salinity or pesticides); and eDNA for rapid screening and targeting. Threshold-only studies should be paired with local time-series to confirm responsiveness before changing policy or standards.

Limitations

- **Single reviewer for screening and extraction**
Introduces selection and interpretation bias.
- **Restricted database coverage**
Relevant studies may be missed, narrowing the evidence base and potentially skewing conclusions.
- **English-only inclusion**
Excludes non-English evidence, which can systematically omit findings from regions where similar interventions have been evaluated.

- **Tight publication date window**
Older but still informative studies may have been excluded, limiting historical context and long-term lessons.
- **Limited coverage of grey literature**
Agency reports and practitioner studies, which are often rich in implementation detail, were under-represented, reducing practical insight into real-world performance.
- **Subject-matter constraints**
The reviewer's expertise may affect how complex methods/results were interpreted.
- **Narrative synthesis only**
Findings rely on qualitative integration. This can propagate imprecision and over- or under-weight particular results.
- **Five-year responsiveness emphasis**
Prioritising indicators that respond ≤ 5 years biases towards "fast" signals and may undervalue slower but valid ecological responses.
- **Geographic skew (Victoria-focused)**
While many regions share similar landscapes and pressures, resource constraints prevented me from systematically calibrating or testing transferability beyond Victoria on a study-by-study basis.

Conclusion

This rapid review finds that Victoria can strengthen MER within five-year cycles by prioritising a small, practical indicator set: macroinvertebrate richness for event responses; selective stressor indices; diatom traits; and eDNA for rapid screening and targeting. Most included studies are high quality, but many are cross-sectional, so they are useful for detection rather than trend inference. Thresholds should be paired with short local time-series and calibration. Substantial evidence gaps remain. Address them by broadening geography and selectively incorporating credible grey literature. Near-term actions include adopting trigger-based thresholds and funding eDNA calibration pilots. Embedding these indicators in MER will de-risk mid-cycle decisions, support adaptive management, and improve transparency.

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Appendix-Collation Table

Lead Author Name	Year Published	Study Design	Sample & Population	Indicator(s) Assessed	Time-to-signal (\$5yr)	Direction & Magnitude	Comparator/Baseline	Study Quality	Comments
Song, K.	2013	Quantitative	Cyanobacterial phycoerythrin (PC) proxy: PC—probe (cells/mL), lab (µg/L); N/A (cross-sectional) subset with lab PC & biovolume	PC—probe (cells/mL), lab (µg/L); N/A (cross-sectional) remote models IBM/SMA05/SV00;	Agreement p obs+models: SA R ² =0.96; IN R ² =0.88; validation RMSE=±1.5–3.4%	Against V3 probe & lab PC; algorithm benchmark king (IBM/SMA05/SV00); OBR/OCL	High Quality	MER use: rapid bloom detection/screening;	
Chattopadhyay, S.	2021	Quantitative	Benthic macroinvertebrates (species-level where possible)	Richness; abundance; BMWP-PI; Shannon evenness (E); Simpson diversity (D); NMDS composition	Yes (weeks-months); full recovery by ~7 weeks post-peak	Abundance ↓ ~42% (Mar→Jul); reach richness ↓ ~27% (4.5→28); BMWP-PI 54→36; E-D 0	Pre-flood March 2020 (before vs after across 8 sites)	High Quality	MER use: trigger-based monitoring supports
Morris, L.	2017	Quantitative	Intertidal infauna (macroinvertebrates)	Infauna abundance (m ⁻²), edible biomass (gm ⁻²), tax richness	Yes (weeks-months) — spring 2014 trigger; recovery by summer 2015	↓ abundance/biomass/richness vs 2011–2013 baseline; biomass crossed ~50% reduction trigger;	mean of spring 2011–2013; treatment classes (effluent/freshwater/control) & season control (spring/summer)	High Quality	MER: trigger-based monitoring supports
Gawne, B.	2013	Synthesis	Water-dependent ecosystems & biota (vegetation, fish, water birds, macroinvertebrates, other vertebrates)	Framework of indicators—ecosystem diversity; vegetation condition; land use; atmospheric indicators; species richness	Yes (framework defines <1 year and 1–5 years expected)	N/A (no empirical effect sizes); articulated expected outcomes only	Program-level evaluation vs Basin Plan EWP objectives; recommends BACI/BAC & Boreas designs;	Uncertain Quality	MER use: cornerstone for CEWO LTM;
Rourke, M.	2024	Quantitative	Golden perch (Macquaria omibiqua)	eDNA concentration (1.25 qPCR copies rxn ⁻¹ / ng L ⁻¹) vs electrophoretic biomass	N/A (cross-sectional; two column compdign)	eDNA—biomass positive at ~1.1–5.5 kg site ⁻¹ ; index >~5.5 kg L ⁻¹ (r ² =0.23)	Benchmark = concurrent elect of fishing; random effects = rivers/sites/years	High Quality	MER: good for detecting
Reich, P.	2023	Quantitative	Benthic macroinvertebrates (family-level) in intermittent streams	Family richness; EPT families; SIGNAL2; functional traits	Not for restoration; 5.5 yr; Yes to hydrological extremes	No significant treatment effect after 6–8 yr	Pre- and control vs restored reaches; pre vs post restoration; covariate-controlled	High Quality	MER: functional-trait metrics respond to flow
Schäfer, R. B.	2011	Quantitative	Macroinvertebrates (family-level indices); minor odg groups on lead packs	SPEAR pesticides; SIGNAL	N/A (cross-sectional; 5-month compdign; not a time series)	SPEAR ↓ with toxicity (R ² =0.67); SIGNAL ↓ (R ² =0.36); strongest links when using sediment MLU (larva)	Toxicity gradient (max: site-level log mTU aggregated across methods/dates); other environmental variables tested	High Quality	MER: use SPEAR as pesticide-selective
Simonin, M.	2021	Quantitative	Bacteria, algae, eukaryotes, macroinvertebrates; fish (multi-marker eDNA)	Toxic richness & community composition; community threshold vs specific	N/A (cross-sectional; single compdign)	Diversity declines ~18–41%; community thresholds ~1.56 (bacterial) 1.68 (fungal)	Reference/low-mortality streams vs mined/below vs above 300 µS/cm EPA criterion	High Quality	MER: conductivity thresholds (~150–200)
Sheldon, F.	2012	Quantitative	Aggregated ecosystem health (fish, macroinvertebrates, water quality, nutrients, ecosystem processes); 14	EHM-F site seasonal score (0–1) and five component indicators	N/A (multi-year monitoring+ modeling; not a 5.5-yr signal test)	Fast near streams ↑ score (MDF HA-HS high inclusion; D/FLO+); urbanization L.A. and roads sites	Land-use gradients of catchment/riparian/reach scales; seasonal (pre- vs post-well & rainfall)	High Quality	MER: aggregated score good for regional
Schmidt, A.M.	2021	Synthesis	Species & habitat types targeted by the Birds & Habitats Directives (inside/outside Natura2000)	Monitoring frameworks; RS; ended EBVs (community composition, ecosystem)	N/A (handbook; no time-series testing)	N/A (no empirical effect sizes reported)	Guidance aligned to 8D Art.11.2 & HD Art.11.7 reporting (on empirical baseline/control comparison)	Uncertain Quality	MER use: consolidates monitoring, remote-
Noble, M.M.	2017	Quantitative	Murray crayfish (Euastacus armatus) — density and size classes	Crayfish density (ind/100 m ²); microhabitat selection (depth, flow, bed composition, boulder)	No (major change detected over 6 years; 2009–2015)	Glide-pools mean density ~91% (2009–2015); boulder cover ~32% & diatom	Meshed/diat control (glide-pool vs riffle run); microhabitat selection vs availability; 2009 vs 2015 in	High Quality	MER: E. armatus is a sensitive focal indicator;
Shackleton, M.E.	2019	Quantitative	Wetland plants (riparian & aquatic); sediment eDNA (18S trnL) + extant plant surveys	Plant community composition (OU)/species	N/A (cross-sectional; no time series)	eDNA patterns mirror extant communities (Rho: trnL OIU)	eDNA community matrices compared to extant survey/matrix (landscape)	High Quality	MER: cost-effective landscape survey;
Frost, C.	2024	Quantitative	Benthic diatoms; aquatic macroinvertebrates (incl. EPT)	Diatom taxonomic & functional diversity (FD); guilds/motility; community composition	Yes (weeks) — responses within 6 weeks	largest shift of +1 mm treatment; diatom richness ↑ but functional	Control (induced substrate) vs added gradients; same on control	High Quality	MER: actionable infaun guideline <1 mm for
Schäfer, R. B.	2011	Quantitative	Benthic macroinvertebrates (family/species level per program)	SPEAR richness (physiological sensitivity); SPEAR biomass; benthic macroinvertebrates; microcosm	N/A (cross-sectional; not a time series test)	%SPEAR richness ↑ with ↑ log EC; R ² ≈ 0.50 (VIC pools); 0.45 (VIC riffles); 0.45 (ISA pools); 0.38 (ISA)	Gradient vs log EC; EC classes (<1000, 1000–3000, >3000 µS/cm) & pesticide EF categories for inter- and on-site	High Quality	MER: Trait-based SPEAR richness prov
Marshall, S.	2010	Quantitative	Benthic macroinvertebrates; microcosm adult Chironomidae (e.g. Loricata)	RBA metrics—AUSRAV AS/OE; SIGNAL Number of Families; Key	N/A (cross-sectional; ~2 months)	RBA vs metrics; SIGNAL R ² =0.35; Families r ² =0.81; Key Families	Reference wetland sediment (Glynnis) & upstem for estuarine sites vs urban	High Quality	MER: combine RBA indices (especially
Kefford, B.J.	2012	Quantitative	Stream insects (macroinvertebrates); species-level where practicable	Families; microcosm community functional traits (feeding groups, size, dispersion, generation length, taxa, breeding, aquatic tolerance)	N/A (cross-sectional)	r ² =0.85 (all inverse, p<0.028); predators ↑ ~1.7%–5.7% with EC; drift/beaters ↑ ~1.3%–4.3%; water-breathers ↓ ~8.2%–40%; riffles: channel	sediments/sites; low vs high-HMX; Low vs higher EC; N/NTU categories; protection threshold R ² 0.95 (r ² =55%	High Quality	MER: structure-based protection can miss trait